

AN EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF NET PRESSURE COEFFICIENT FOR MULTI-STOREY BUILDING USING AN EIFFEL TYPE WIND TUNNEL TO GENERATE A COMPRESSIBLE AERODYNAMIC FREE STREAM FLOW

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ABSTRACT

The research work focuses on the experimental determination of net pressure coefficient for 72m, 20-storey building using an Eiffel type wind tunnel to generate a compressible aerodynamic free stream flow. By using mathematical models developed by notable scholars; some of the grey areas leading to confusion in the use of the terms compressible and incompressible flow were discussed. Subsequently, two models of scale 1: 300 for model height were constructed with Afra timber because it was easy to machine to various shapes and sizes. Pipettes, brazen and suitable flexible rubber tubes were used for the construction of the improvised manometer used to measure the external pressure around the perimeter of the models. A scale of 1: 3 was used for site (i.e.52 ms⁻¹; Bauchi - Nigeria) – Tunnel (i.e.17.5 ms⁻¹) wind speed. The investigation shows that, there is equilibrium of the pressure between the static and the dynamic pressures at a value of 81mm. The maximum and minimum values for the static and dynamic pressures are respectively 112mm / 48.5mm and 125mm / 33mm respectively. Similarly, the net pressure distributions of the four faces (A, B, C and D) of the model were investigated and the pressure increases with a maximum at the model height of 152mm (C). The value at this height is approximately 1.28. Above this height there is a drop of approximately 3.13% but the average net external pressure coefficient is 1.187. This value differs by 1.10% from 1.2 recommended by BS 6399; part 2 (2004).

KEYWORDS: Wind Tunnel, compressible and incompressible flows, Piezometric heads, manometer, static and dynamic pressures

INTRODUCTION

According to Mihailovic *et al.*, (2004) many complex environmental features at small, medium, or large scales involve processes that occur both within and between environmental media (e.g., air, surface water, groundwater, soil, biota). Considerable recent research work addresses various aspects of modeling these processes using new methodologies/approaches, numerical methods, and software techniques (e.g., Janjic *et al.* 2001; Lalic *et al.* 2003; Mihailovic *et al.* 2001 and 2002).

According to Ristic *et al.*; (2010) nowadays worldwide, various experimental and numerical methods are used for airfoils or hydrofoils pressure coefficient (C_p) determination. Besides the conventional methods for C_p determination, through measurements of pressure distributions on models surface by tips and pressure transducers, (using scanivalves or electronically scanned pressure sensors, smart sensors, miniaturized devices, pressure sensors based on electro active materials, balk or saw sensors, optical fiber tip pressure sensors and so on) non-contact methods are implemented more and more. Most frequently used methods are interferometry (classical or holographic), LDA, PIV, pressure sensitive paints, micro sensors and so on. These methods do not require models with small holes on the surface and do not cause disturbances in the flow.

Also according to Clancy (1975), the pressure coefficient is a dimensionless number which describes the relative pressures throughout a flow field in fluid dynamics. The pressure coefficient is used in aerodynamics and hydrodynamics. Every point in a fluid flow field has its own unique pressure coefficient (C_p). In many situations in aerodynamics and hydrodynamics, the pressure coefficient at a point near a body is independent of body size. Consequently an engineering model can be tested in a wind tunnel or water tunnel, pressure coefficients can be

determined at critical locations around the model, and these pressure coefficients can be used with confidence to predict the fluid pressure at those critical locations around a full-size aircraft or boat and or including tall structures such as multi-storey buildings. It is common for some researchers and scientist to confuse or interchange the use of the word compressible and incompressible flow when solving important scientific and engineering problems. Therefore, this research work has two main objectives. 1. To use the mathematical relationships of some notable scholars to support the explanations' of the relevant scientific and engineering applications of the concepts compressible and incompressible flow as they relate to the determination of pressure coefficients; and 2. To also attempt to use experimental methods to determine the net pressure coefficient for 72m, 20 storey building using an Eiffel type wind tunnel by testing the model peripheral Piezometric pressure points through the connected manometer and suitable flexible rubber tubes.

Concept of Compressible and Incompressible Flows

The application of the analytical geometry derivation of the concept of fluid mechanics or more generally continuum mechanics and incompressible flow (isochoric flow) refers to a flow in which the material density is constant within a fluid parcel – an infinitesimal volume that moves with the velocity of the fluid. An equivalent statement implying incompressibility is that, the divergence of the fluid velocity is zero, which illustrates why these conditions are equivalent (Durrant 1989 and Almgren *et al*; 2006).

According to the works of Durrant (1989) and Almgren *et al*; (2006) incompressible flow does not imply that the fluid itself is incompressible. It is shown in the derivations that (under the right conditions) even compressible fluids can – to good approximation – be modelled as an incompressible flow. Incompressible flow implies that the density remains constant within a parcel of fluid which moves with the fluid velocity. The fundamental requirement for incompressible flow is that the density, ρ , is constant within an infinitesimal volume, dV , which moves at the velocity of the fluid, v . Mathematically, this constraint implies that the material derivative of the density must vanish to ensure incompressible flow. Before introducing this constraint, we must apply the conservation of mass to generate the necessary relations. The mass is calculated by a volume integral of the density,

$$\rho: \\ m = \iiint_V \rho dV \quad \dots 1$$

The conservation of mass requires that the time derivative of the mass inside a control volume be equal to the mass flux, J , across its boundaries. Mathematically, we can represent this constraint in terms of a surface integral equation (2) (Durrant, 1989):

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial t} = - \oint_S (J \cdot ds) \quad \dots 2$$

The negative sign in equation (2) ensures that outward flow results in a decrease in the mass with respect to time, using the convention that the surface area vector points outward. Now, using the divergence theorem, we can derive the relationship between the flux and the partial time derivative of the density:

$$\iiint_V \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} dV = - \iiint_V (\nabla \cdot J) dV \quad \dots 3$$

Therefore:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot J \quad \dots 4$$

The works of Durrant, (1989) also so that the partial derivative of the density with respect to time need not vanish to ensure incompressible *flow*; when we speak of the partial derivative of the density with respect to time, we are referring to this rate of change within a control volume of fixed position (i.e. such as we have in a multi-storey building). By allowing the partial time derivative of the density to be non-zero, we are not restricting ourselves to

incompressible fluids because the density is allowed to change as observed from a fixed position as fluid flows through the control volume. This approach maintains generality, and not requiring that the partial time derivative of the density vanishes illustrates that compressible fluids can still undergo incompressible flow. What we are interested in now is the change in density of a control volume which moves along with the fluid velocity, \mathbf{v} . The mass flux, \mathbf{J} is related to the fluid velocity through the following function equation (5):

$$\mathbf{J} = \rho \mathbf{v} \quad \dots 5$$

So that the conservation of mass implies that:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \rho \cdot \mathbf{v} + \rho (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) = 0 \quad \dots 6$$

The relation where we have used the appropriate product rule is known as the continuity equation. Now, we need the following relation about the total derivative of the density (where we apply the chain rule):

$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} = \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} \frac{dx}{dt} + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial y} \frac{dy}{dt} + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z} \frac{dz}{dt} \quad \dots 7$$

So if we choose a control volume that is moving at the same rate as the fluid (i.e. $(dx/dt, dy/dt, dz/dt) = \mathbf{v}$), then this expression simplifies to the material derivative:

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \rho \cdot \mathbf{v} \quad \dots 8$$

And so using the continuity equation derived above, we see that:

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \quad \dots 8a$$

A change in the density over time would imply that, the fluid had either compressed or expanded (or that the mass contained in our constant volume, dV , had changed), which we have prohibited. We must then require that the material derivative of the density vanishes, and equivalently (for non-zero density) so must the divergence of the fluid velocity:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0, \quad \dots 8b$$

And so beginning with the conservation of mass and the constraint that the density within a moving volume of fluid remains constant, it has been shown that an equivalent condition required for incompressible flow is that the divergence of the fluid velocity vanishes (Almgren *et al*; 2006).

In some fields, a measure of the incompressibility of a flow is the change in density as a result of the pressure variations. This is best expressed in terms of the compressibility (Almgren *et al*; 2006).

$$\beta = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{dp} \quad \dots 9$$

Durran 1989, Almgren *et al*; (2006) if the compressibility is acceptably small, the flow is considered to be incompressible. An incompressible flow is described by a velocity field which is solenoidal. But a solenoidal field, besides having a zero divergence, also has the additional connotation of having non-zero curl (i.e., rotational

component). Otherwise, if an incompressible flow also has a curl of zero, so that it is also irrotational, then the velocity field is actually Laplacian. As defined earlier, an incompressible (isochoric) flow is the one in which.

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \quad \dots 10$$

This is equivalent to saying that

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = \frac{\partial\rho}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla\rho = 0 \quad \dots 11$$

The material derivative of the density is zero. Thus if we follow a material element, its mass density will remain constant. Note that the material derivative consists of two terms. The first term $\frac{\partial\rho}{\partial t}$ describes how the density of the material element changes with time. This term is also known as the *unsteady term*. The second term, $\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla\rho$ describes the changes in the density as the material element moves from one point to another (i.e. the type we have along a multi-storey building as it vibrates when subjected to aerodynamic pulsation). This is the *convection* or the *advection term*. For a flow to be incompressible the sum of these terms should be zero. On the other hand, a homogeneous, incompressible material is defined as one which has constant density throughout. For such a material, $\rho = \text{constant}$. This implies that,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial\rho}{\partial t} = 0 & \quad \text{and} \\ \nabla\rho = 0 & \quad \text{independently} \end{aligned} \quad \dots 11a$$

From the continuity equation it follows that

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = \frac{\partial\rho}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla\rho = 0 \implies \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad \dots 11b$$

Thus homogeneous materials always undergo flow that is incompressible, but the converse is not true. It is common to find references where the author mentions incompressible flow and assumes that density is constant. Even though this is technically incorrect, it is an accepted practice. One of the advantages of using the incompressible material assumption over the incompressible flow assumption is in the momentum equation where the kinematic viscosity ($\nu = \frac{\mu}{\rho}$) can be assumed to be constant. The subtlety above is frequently a source of confusion. Therefore many people prefer to refer explicitly to *incompressible materials* or *isochoric flow* when being descriptive about the mechanics.

When related to constraints in fluid dynamics, a flow is considered to be incompressible if the divergence of the velocity is zero. However, related formulations can sometimes be used, depending on the flow system to be modelled. Some versions are described as follows:

- i. *Incompressible flow*: $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$. This can assume either constant density (strict incompressible) or varying density flow. The varying density set accepts solutions involving small perturbations in density, pressure and/or temperature fields, and can allow for pressure stratification in the domain.
- ii. *Anelastic flow*: $\nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{u}) = 0$. Principally used in the field of atmospheric sciences, the anelastic constraint extends incompressible flow validity to stratified density and / or temperature as well as pressure. This allows the thermodynamic variables to relax to an 'atmospheric' base state seen in the lower atmosphere when used in the field of meteorology, for example. This condition can also be used for various astrophysical systems (Durrant, 1989).

- iii. *Low Mach-number flow / Pseudo-incompressibility:* $\nabla \cdot (\alpha \mathbf{u}) = \beta$. The low Mach-number constraint can be derived from the compressible Euler equations using scale analysis of non-dimensional quantities. The restraint, like the previous in this section, allows for the removal of acoustic waves, but also allows for *large* perturbations in density and/or temperature. The assumption is that; the flow remains within a Mach number limit which is normally less than 0.3 for any solution using such a constraint to be valid. Again, in accordance with all incompressible flows the pressure deviation must be small in comparison to the pressure base state (Almgren *et al.*; 2006).

A. Incompressible flow

Therefore, the pressure coefficient is a parameter for studying the flow of incompressible fluids such as water, and also the low-speed flow of compressible fluids such as air. The relationship between the dimensionless coefficient and the dimensional numbers is equation (12) (Abbott and Doenhoff, 1959 and Clancy, 1975).

$$C_p = \frac{p - p_\infty}{\frac{1}{2} \rho_\infty V_\infty^2} \quad \dots 12$$

Where

- p is the pressure at the point at which pressure coefficient is being evaluated
- p_∞ is the pressure in the freestream (i.e. remote from any disturbance)
- ρ_∞ is the free stream fluid density (Air at sea level and 15 °C is 1.225 kg/m^3)
- V_∞ is the free stream velocity of the fluid, or the velocity of the body through the fluid

Using Bernoulli's Equation, the pressure coefficient can be further simplified for incompressible, lossless, and steady flow (Anderson 2001).

$$C_p = 1 - \left(\frac{V}{V_\infty} \right)^2 \quad \dots 12a$$

Where

V is the velocity of the fluid at the point at which pressure coefficient is being evaluated.

This relationship is also valid for the flow of compressible fluids where variations in speed and pressure are sufficiently small that variations in fluid density can be ignored. This is a reasonable assumption when the Mach Number is less than about 0.3 (Anderson 2001).

- i. $C_p = 0$ indicates the pressure is the same as the free stream pressure.
- ii. $C_p = 1$ indicates the pressure is stagnation pressure and the point is a stagnation point.
- iii. $C_p = -1$ is significant in the design of gliders because this indicates a perfect location for a "Total energy" port for supply of signal pressure to the Variometer, a special Vertical Speed Indicator which reacts to vertical movements of the atmosphere but does not react to vertical maneuvering of the glider.

In the fluid flow field around a body there will be points having positive pressure coefficients up to one, and negative pressure coefficients including coefficients less than minus one, but nowhere will the coefficient exceed plus one because the highest pressure that can be achieved is the stagnation pressure. The only time the coefficient will exceed plus one is when advanced boundary layer control techniques, such as blowing, are used.

B. Compressible flow

In the flow of compressible fluids such as air, and particularly the high-speed flow of compressible fluids, $\rho v^2/2$ (the dynamic pressure) is no longer an accurate measure of the difference between stagnation pressure and

static pressure. Also, the familiar relationship that stagnation pressure is equal to *total pressure* does not always hold true. (It is always true in isentropic flow but the presence of shock waves can cause the flow to depart from isentropic.) As a result, pressure coefficients can be greater than one in compressible flow (Anderson 2001).

When C_p is greater than one; indicates the free stream flow is compressible.

$$C_p = \frac{\rho}{\gamma M_\infty^2} \left(\frac{P}{P_\infty} - 1 \right) \quad \dots\dots 13$$

Where

γ = Adiabatic index

M_∞ = Mach Number

C. Pressure Distribution

An airfoil at a given angle of attack will have what is called a pressure distribution. This pressure distribution is simply the pressure at all points around an airfoil. Typically, graphs of these distributions are drawn so that negative numbers are higher on the graph, as the C_p for the upper surface of the airfoil will usually be farther below zero and will hence be the top line on the graph.

Experimental Determination of the Net Pressure Coefficient

i. Proto -Type Location and Model Parameters

A prototype model of 20 storeys building (Hp=72 m, Bp =13 m and Wp=25 m) was tested in an Eiffel-Type boundary layer wind tunnel using a physical model of Hm=240 mm, Wm=83.3 mm, Bm= 43.3 mm constructed of a deformable Afara Wood (that is, rectangular and hollow mounted on steel base and Polystyrene). The prototype frequency fp,= 0.534 Hz (fm=53.4 Hz), Prototype – model building scale 1 : 300 and Prototype – model wind scale 1 : 3. A Prevailing basic wind speed of 52.5 m/s was considered for Bauchi - Nigeria. Bauchi is located at an elevation of approximately 610 m above sea level. The physical and mechanical characteristics of these materials are respectively shown in (Onundi *et al*; 2012).

Model Materials

The model dimension scale is 1: 300. The materials used for the construction of the model are as follows:

- a.) Afara wood
- b.) Mild steel and
- c.) Polystyrene

The Afara wood was used for the construction of the superstructure. Afara is relatively easy to machine to the desired shapes and sizes. The Afara wood was used for the construction of the model to ensure that a low mass is produced. As long as the structural geometry does not change, the forces can be used to analyze the effects of internal structural design changes without the need for further wind tunnel tests (Mendis *et al.*; 2007). The mild steel is used for the base plate which represents an infinitely rigid foundation. This rests on the polystyrene and is assumed to behave as soil on elastic foundation. Its impact on the structural integrity of the model also influences the degree of damping incorporated within the system (Onundi *et al*; 2012).

Wind Tunnel Experiment

a.) Wind Tunnel Specifications

The wind tunnel experiment was conducted using the Eiffel-Type boundary layer wind tunnel which is a close circuit type for the experimental setup. The wind tunnel and other fluid related equipment were housed in a room of about 10 m by 20 m in plan and 4.2 m high along with other thermodynamics equipment at the fluid and thermodynamics laboratory. It consists of an aerofoil axial fan driven by a variable speed d.c. electric motor and mounted centrally between the diffuser and the test chamber. This is used to create a jet of air in the test chamber. The model was mounted in a test chamber measuring about 410 mm x 570 mm x 300 mm. The wind tunnel's test chamber has an access (outlet or inlet) which is square in shape with a dimension of 300 mm x 300mm.

b. Model construction

Two models were construction using a ratio of 1:2:6 for the width, breadth and height. The component parts of the model were machined to the desired shapes and sizes. The cross sections for the walls of the two models are 10 mm thick (Onundi *et al.*; 2012). The assembling of the models was achieved using a set of G - clamping devices. The hollow rectangular cross-sections of the walls were joined together using special adhesives such as epoxy resin and liquid glue. Diaphragms of 10mm thick were installed beside the wind tunnel and they are made of Afara wood. The diaphragms have provisions for the connection of wires and rubbers from the model to the manometer. The base of the model is mounted on a flat steel plate. This is expected to serve as an infinitely rigid foundation resting on the polystyrene. This arrangement represents the soil conditions and is assumed to behave as elastic base.

At the sides and various levels of the models, fourteen (14) pressure brazen tubes of 1mm diameter each were installed for measuring the Piezometric heads around the model walls. These pressure measuring (Piezometric) points were achieved by using bent brazen tubes with internal and external diameters of approximately 1mm and 3 mm respectively. These were fixed with 25mm nails to the inner surfaces of the model walls. In the working chamber, two (2) brazen tubes were also installed for monitoring the static (P_{st}) and dynamic (P_d) pressures.

c. Distribution of the wind pressures through the Piezometric heads

As shown in Figures (1and 2), two models were used for this experimental setup. Each model has four elevations labeled as A, B, C and D respectively. The arrangements of the first alternates the second such that areas and levels not covered or measured by the first model were successfully measured by the second. The use of two models became necessary because of the size of the brazen tubes used for these measurements. The idea of using the two models is to reduce congestion of the pipes entering the model at the same level. A total of 28 Piezometric points were installed; 14 (fourteen) for each model. In addition to the 28 installed Piezometric heads, eight (8) Piezometric heads were also installed to monitor the static (P_{st}) and dynamic (P_d) pressures within the test chamber. The brazen tubes were all connected to the improvised manometer using suitable flexible rubber tubes. The total number, distribution of the Piezometric heads on the four faces (A, B, C and D) and heights of the model are shown in Table1 B and D are the windward and leeward sides respectively.

Table 1: Piezometric Heads Distribution for the Determination of the Wind Pressure

Elevation	Model Heights (mm)	Number Installed
A	25	7
B	88	7
C	152	7
D	215	7
Total		28

Figure 1: Isometric Views of Piezometric Points (Wind Pressure Distribution)

Figure 2 : Wind Tunnel Test Setup

Calibration of the wind speed

The wind tunnel has facilities for varying the wind speed and this is calibrated into three main gauges ($U_{3.5}$, $U_{5.4}$ and U_7) respectively. From the past work of Soboyejo (1971), the wind speed for Bauchi is 52.5 ms^{-1} and using the model ratio of 1: 3, the tunnel wind speed is assumed to be 17.5 ms^{-1} .

The wind speed readings were recorded using a Hot Wire Anemometer RS 327-0640 (Q268850). Three readings were taken at the bottom, middle and top of every point of the gauge setting of the wind tunnel test chamber and the values are given in Table 2 and Figure 3

Determination of the net pressure coefficient

Applying the tunnel wind speed of 17.5 ms^{-1} to the model, the pressure acting on the model were measured at 28 points on the four vertical faces (A, B, C and D) at different levels corresponding to the second, seventh, thirteenth and eighteenth floor levels which are (25 mm, 88 mm, 152 mm and 215 mm above ground level Figures 4 (a and b). The suction emanating from the wind pressures acting on the model were measured using the manometer to produce the values of Piezometric heads (P_i) presented in Figure 5. There were 8 additional points introduced and also measured using the manometer. Four points were for the measurement of the static pressures, (P_{st}) and the remaining four for the dynamic pressure (P_d). Their values are also presented in Figure 5. Using these values; the net wind pressure coefficient (C_{pi}) for the model is determined using (Manko and Wdowiak, 1996).

$$C_{pi} = \frac{P_i - P_{st}}{P_d} \quad \dots(14)$$

where,

C_{pi} = Net pressure coefficient for the model determined as 1.187.

P_i = Piezometric heads (i.e. Static pressures) at point i. (where i. varies from 1 to 28 along the models)

P_{st} = Static pressure along the model or within the test chamber

P_d = Dynamic pressure

Table 2: Measurement of Wind Speed within the Tunnel's Test Chamber

Gauge Setting	Bottom (ms^{-1})	Middle (ms^{-1})	Top (ms^{-1})
U_7	26	26	26
$U_{5.4}$	20	18.1	17
$U_{3.5}$	14	14	14

Figure 3: Measurement of Wind Speed within the Tunnel's Test Chamber

(a) Front and Rear Elevations : Sides B and D)

(b) Sides Elevations: Sides (A and C)

Figure 4: Piezometric Points on the Elevations (Wind Pressure Distribution)

Figure 5 : Piezometric Heads on Elevations

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the measurement of wind speed within the tunnel’s test chamber. It is this Table that produced the calibrated and interpolated wind speed of 17.5 ms^{-1} that corresponds to the 1: 3 scales which relate the wind speed on site in Bauchi (52.5 ms^{-1}) to the wind speed achievable in the wind tunnel test chamber as shown in Figure 3.

This influenced the suction that produced the pressure distributions recorded on the four faces of the model. Figure 6 was derived from Figure 5; it therefore shows the pressure distributions recorded on the four faces (A, B, C and D) of the model. The wind distribution characteristics on faces A and B are similar and convex in shape, while the wind distribution on faces C and D are divergent in nature. The reasons for such behavior could be adduced from the factors generally considered on the wind characteristics on Models. These are:

- i.) wind turbulence (temporal and spatial fluctuation of wind)
- ii.) vortex generated in wake of building
- iii.) interaction between building

The effect of the wind behaviour on faces A, B, and D is compressive in nature and the highest Piezometric head (pressure) was recorded for side D (138.6mm), while the lowest record at face A is 20.9mm.

Looking at Figure 7, which is a magnified behaviour of face C from Figure 6, it will be seen that it is the face that is most adversely affected. This produces suction of the magnitude of -1.4. Figure 8 shows the distribution of static and dynamic pressures. It was observed that at 5.4, there is equilibrium of the pressure between the static and the dynamic pressures given a value 81mm. The maximum and minimum values for the static and dynamic pressures are respectively 112mm / 48.5mm and 125mm / 33mm.

Figure 9 show the net pressure distribution of the four faces (A, B, C and D) of the model. The pressure increases with a maximum at the model height of 152mm (C). The value at this height is approximately 1.28. Above this height there is a drop of approximately 3.13%. Averagely, all the values give a net pressure coefficient of 1.187. The British Standard BS 6399 Part 2 (2005) gave C_{pi} to be approximately 1.2. This gives a difference of about 1.10% higher than the value derived from the model. The differences may have arisen from the errors recorded using the improvised manometer and the vortices that may have developed as a result of the obstructions caused by the flexible rubber tubes.

Figure9: Pressure Distribution

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